

University of Toronto Libraries Scoping Decision Tree for Paid AI-Powered Research Tools

Can the library license this AI tool?

About

This decision tree is designed for collections librarians and information professionals at the University of Toronto who are considering submitting requests for AI-powered research tools related to library collections that have an associated cost.

As libraries navigate the rapidly evolving landscape of AI technologies, this framework provides a structured guide to help determine which tools might align with our licensing capabilities and institutional priorities.

These considerations are not intended to provide definitive acceptance or rejection decisions, but rather to guide your preliminary assessment process. These questions may help you identify if a respective AI-powered research tool warrants further investigation, the possibility that tools unsuitable for library licensing may be appropriate for other university units to consider, or which present challenges may need to be addressed before licensing can be considered.

The decision tree encourages thoughtful evaluation of factors including licensing models, target audience alignment, the capability for users to opt-out, and cost considerations.

Remember that these questions represent initial scoping criteria only - tools that appear within scope will still require further evaluation regarding privacy implications, data security, integration capabilities, and alignment with library values before final licensing decisions are made.

If your initial assessment suggests that an AI-powered research tool may be within scope for licensing by the library, please contact your collections specialist or coordinator to discuss further.

A text-only version follows the provided graphic.

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While the AI-powered research tool may be in scope at this stage, further evaluation will be required before a final licensing decision is made. Consult with the collections coordinator in your area to proceed with next steps.

Scoping Decision Tree for Licensing Paid AI-Powered Research Tools

1. Can another unit at the University feasibly license this AI-Powered research tool? e.g. Teaching & Learning, ITS, CTSI; is this a third-party standalone tool with which the library has no pre-existing relationship?
 - a. If yes, the tool is not currently in scope for the library to license.
 - b. If maybe, consult with the collections coordinator in your area to discuss further.
 - c. If no, proceed to the next question.

2. Is the licensing model conducive to the library licensing this AI-Powered research tool? E.g. Under what terms is the AI-powered search tool licensed? Are the terms suitable for our users? Is it related to a consortia or institutional licensed product?
 - a. If yes, proceed to the next question.
 - b. If no, the tool is not currently in scope. Return to question one to consider if the tool can be licensed by another unit on campus.

3. Is the target audience of the AI-Powered research tool University of Toronto students, faculty, and researchers?
 - a. If yes, proceed to the next question.
 - b. If no, the tool is not currently in scope. Return to question one to consider if the tool can be licensed by another unit on campus.

4. Does the AI-powered research tool have the capability for users to opt-out of its use?
 - a. If yes, proceed to the next question.
 - b. If no, the tool is not currently in scope.

5. Is the cost of the AI-Powered research tool reasonable?
 - a. If yes, the tool may be within scope for licensing by the library.
 - b. If no, the tool is not currently in scope.

While the AI-powered research tool may be in scope at this stage, further evaluation will be required before a final licensing decision is made.

Consult with the collections coordinator in your area to proceed with next steps.